

THE CRITERION OF MOVEMENT IN JAPANESE NPs

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The purpose of this paper is to prove that the process of definiteness in Japanese is not a hazardous one, but it is deeply motivated by syntactic phenomenology. As a matter of fact, we will show that there are certain restrictions at stake which argue in favor of our thesis, and these restrictions are further backed up by syntactic phenomena that determine the projections. One such phenomenon is the criterion of movement, which can be observed in the case of post-nominal phrases. One domain of research will be the pre-nominal NC which we will show it allows ellipsis, much in the opinion of Watanabe (2006). This demonstration will help us with our thesis in that it supports the point of view that definiteness can occur in articleless languages like Japanese, which exhibits a large plethora of linguistically heterogeneous methods for the expression of definite or indefinite Noun Phrase.

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11.2. The Criterion of Movement

One important syntactic phenomenon, apart from restriction, is that of movement which can be observed in the case of post nominal phrases. As Takahashi (2008) demonstrates, it is in principle possible to elide the NP complement of the post-nominal NC.

1. Bushu-wa [jibun-ni kansuru hon] 2-satsu-o yonda.

Bush-Top self-Dat related book 2-CL-Acc read

Obama-wa 3-satsu-o yonda.

Obama-Top 3-CL-Acc read

'Bush read two books about himself. Obama read three.'

He then provides another example to confirm that there is a syntactic process at stake with regard to the definite or indefinite interpretation of the Noun Phrase. More specifically, as shown below, the floating NC is fine in this type of context while the post-nominal NC is not, arguing in favor of his presumption:

2. a. Tomoko-wa 30-sai made-ni kodomo-o 2-ri um-itai to omotteiru.

Tomoko-Top 30-year old by-Dat child-Acc 2-CL bear-want that think

'Tomoko feels that she wants to give birth to 2 children by the age of 30.'

b. *Tomoko-wa 30-sai made-ni kodomo 2-ri-o um-itai to omotteiru.

Tomoko-Top 30-year old by-Dat child 2-CL-Acc bear-want that think

'Tomoko feels that she wants to give birth to 2 children by the age of 30.'

Now we are ready to test the prediction of the above hypothesis. The following example has the floating NC in the first clause, which does not have a specific reading, and the second clause is intended to be derived from the post-nominal NC with the NP complement of the CL elided (Huang, 2014:10)

3. Tomoko-wa 30-sai made-ni kodomo-o 2-ri um-itai to omotteiru.

Tomoko-Top 30-year old by-Dat child-Acc 2-CL bear-want that think

'Tomoko feels that she wants to give birth to 2 children by the age of 30.'

*Hanako-wa 25-sai made-ni 3-nin-o um-itai to omotteiru.

Hanako-Top 25-year old by-Dat 3-CL-Acc bear-want that think

'Hanako feels that she wants to give birth to 3 children by the age of 25.'

In these two examples we see that, unlike (396), the elision of a complement is not allowed formally, which means, in the opinion of the author, that the interpretation of a definite NP is linked to movement. Nominal-internal ellipsis is yet another domain in which the pre-nominal and post-nominal NC behave differently. Turning to Japanese, observe first that the pre-nominal NC nominal in Japanese does not allow ellipsis, as pointed out by Saito&all. (2

4. *Taroo-wa [san-satuohon]-o katta ga, Hanako-wa [go-satu-no hon]-o katta.

Taro-Top three-CL-Gen book-Acc bought though Hanako-Top five-CL-Gen book-Acc bought

'Taroo bought three books, but Hanako bought five.'

On the other hand, as we already saw in (396), the post-nominal NC nominal does allow NP ellipsis (see Takahashi 2008), which is confirmed by the fact that the example allows both strict and sloppy readings. This difference naturally follows from our non-uniform view of the adnominal NC. Assuming that the pre-nominal NC always occurs inside the NP, the lowest nominal projection, it follows that there is no maximal projection within

the nominal domain to the exclusion of the pre-nominal NC, which is why examples like

(26) are bad. Watanabe (2010) argues that the pre-nominal NC does in fact allow ellipsis, contrary to Saito et al.'s claim. Watanabe claims that examples like the following may come from the pre-nominal NC source (as well as from the floating one):

5. a. Taroo-wa [san-satu-no hon]-o katta ga, Hanako-wa go-satu katta.

Taro-Top three-CL-Gen book-Acc bought though Hanako-Top five-CL bought

'Taroo bought three books, but Hanako bought five.'

b. Hanako-wa [go-satu ~~hon~~]-o katta.

But there is evidence that examples like (399a) are derived from the floating NC

construction, and not from the pre-nominal NC construction. As Nakanishi (2012) points out, the floating NC typically has a distributive reading, which becomes salient when a predicate like *koros-* 'kill' is used (*Five men killed Taro*)

6. a. go-nin-no otoko-ga Taro-o koroshita. b. otoko go-nin-ga Taro-o koroshita.

*five-CL-Gen man-Nom Taro-Acc killed
man five-CL-Nom Taro-Acc killed*

c. *otoko-ga go-nin Taro-o koroshita.
man-Nom five-CL Taro-Acc killed

With this point in mind, let us reconsider (399). If (399b) can be derived from the pre-nominal NC construction (as well as from the floating NC), as Watanabe claims, then

the following example should be acceptable, contrary to the fact.

7. kyonen *san-nin-no* otoko-ga jiroo-o koroshita.
*last year three-CL-Gen man-Nom Jiro-Acc killed
this year five-CL Taro-Acc killed*

'Last year three men killed Jiro.

*Kotoshi *go-nin taroo-o* koroshita.
this year five-CL Taro-Acc killed

This year, five men killed Taro.'

This shows that (399b) is derived only from the floating NC source. Witness the

following paradigm as a confirmation of this conclusion.

8. a. kotoshi go-nin-no otoko-ga taroo-o koroshita.
this year five-CL-Gen man-Nom Taro-Acc killed
(pre-nominal NC)

b. kotoshi otoko go-nin-ga taroo-o koroshita.
this year man five-CL-Nom Taro-Acc killed
(post-nominal NC)

c. *kotoshi otoko-ga go-nin taroo-o koroshita.
this year man-Nom five-CL Taro-Acc killed
(floating NC)

Our conclusion that examples like (399) involve a pre-nominal NC in the first clause and a floating NC in the second indicates that the parallelism constraint on ellipsis is not sensitive to the distinction between the pre-nominal NC and the floating NC. This point is important as we will explore in the next section the hypothesis that the floating NC involves movement of NP out of a larger nominal domain while the pre-nominal NC does not. Now let us reconsider (24) in this light.

By the same reasoning, the NP complement of the classifier head in the second clause should not be forced to move by parallelism considerations. The unacceptability of (24) therefore militates against the PF-driven nature of NP-movement involved in deriving the post-nominal NC. That is, the movement to spec of XP is not triggered by a PF requirement of Num-CL adjacency, but for a separate, formal reason.

11.2.1. Conclusions of This Section

We have shown that the position of the Nominal Phrase within Japanese bears influence on the dichotomy between definite and indefinite readings for nouns. There are three possible position for classifiers in Japanese, namely pre-nominal, floating and post-nominal, with the latter bearing, most often than not, a specific interpretation. In all three cases the link between the noun and the classifier+numeral construction is inalienable and they usually form a compound NP the specificity of which resides on syntactic grounds. Even though it would pose serious risks to suppose that the contextual reference is not playing its role in these situations, we tried to emphasize that in all of three cases the semantic interpretation of the clauses has syntactic phenomena residing at its core, most notably, that of restriction and movement.

Another important conclusion of this section is also underlined in the previous paragraphs and it deals with the nature of the specific noun in Japanese. As stated before, according to Huang (2014) the definite interpretation is strongly linked to movement in Japanese and we brought into discussion some examples that emphasize his idea. In other words, the complement of the Noun Phrase within the Classifier Phrase cannot be elided without movement as shown in (24), arguing in favor of our syntactically driven thesis for the nature of definiteness in Japanese. There are also restrictions at stake, the most important of which are related to the existential locational verb (Kishimoto, 2000) meaning that when it expresses a possessive relation, the object cannot be specific or presuppositional. His observation is important to our thesis because it underlines that there are important syntactic processes behind the definite or indefinite readings of a noun in Japanese.

The ellision of nouns in order to render the classifier and numeral constructions singular in predicative contexts brings into discussion the grammaticality of these Classifier Phrases which can exist on their own without the implication of a noun. This happens in examples like 27(b) and is somehow illustrated in 22 and 24 as well, but bearing other consequences, namely that of the influence of anaphoricity and contextual references for the definite or indefinite interpretation of post-nominal constructions with classifiers and numerals. By discussing the importance of positions in Japanese regarding specificity we brought into discussion another syntactic character of classifiers, namely that which describes them as topic sensitive lexemes.

References

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